

Supplemental table S1 Spatial navigation performance in participants with Limbic-predominant age-related TDP-43 encephalopathy

		F	P	Variables	Mean difference	95% CI	P_{post-hoc}
Egocentric heading task	Diagnosis	7.845	<.001	CN vs. AD aMCI	0.203	0.094 – 0.313	<.001
				CN vs. LATE aMCI	0.224	0.073 – 0.376	<.001
				AD aMCI vs. LATE aMCI	0.021	-0.121 – 0.163	.770
	Section	0.079	.778				
	Diagnosis * Section	1.421	.243				
Allocentric location task	Diagnosis	18.172	<.001	CN vs. AD aMCI	-27.787	-37.189 – -18.385	<.001
				CN vs. LATE aMCI	-9.240	-22.120 – 3.640	.157
				AD aMCI vs. LATE aMCI	18.547	6.466 – 30.628	.003
	Section	0.314	.575				

	Diagnosis * Section	1.402	.247				
Allocentric heading task	Diagnosis	21.260	<.001	CN vs. AD aMCI	0.299	0.204 – 0.395	<.001
				CN vs. LATE aMCI	0.292	0.160 – 0.423	<.001
				AD aMCI vs. LATE aMCI	-0.008	-0.131 – 0.115	.898
	Section	17.589	<.001	Section 1 vs. Section 2	0.220	0.117 – 0.323	<.001
	Diagnosis * Section	3.738	.025	Section 1: CN vs. AD aMCI	0.222	0.112 – 0.332	<.001
				Section 1: CN vs. LATE aMCI	0.254	0.106 – 0.402	<.001
				Section 1: AD aMCI vs. LATE aMCI	0.032	-0.111 – 0.176	.656
				Section 2: CN vs. AD aMCI	0.377	0.267 – 0.488	<.001
				Section 2: CN vs. LATE aMCI	0.329	0.178 – 0.480	<.001
				Section 2: AD aMCI vs. LATE aMCI	-0.048	-0.195 – 0.098	0.516

F and *P* values refer to the main effect. *P*_{post-hoc} values in bold were significant after false discovery rate (FDR) correction.

95% CI, 95% confidence interval; CN, cognitively normal; AD aMCI, amnesic mild cognitive impairment with positive Alzheimer's disease biomarkers; LATE aMCI, amnesic mild cognitive impairment due to Limbic-predominant age-related TDP-43 encephalopathy.

Supplemental table S2 Spatial navigation performance controlled for the MMSE score

		F	P	Variables	Mean difference	95% CI	<i>P</i>_{post-hoc}
Egocentric heading task	Diagnosis	4.165	.018	CN vs. non-AD aMCI	0.164	0.041 – 0.287	.010
				CN vs. AD aMCI	0.165	0.033 – 0.297	.015
				non-AD aMCI vs. AD aMCI	0.001	-0.115 – 0.118	.986
	Section	1.539	.215				
	Diagnosis * Section	1.664	.191				
Allocentric location task	Diagnosis	8.887	<.001	CN vs. non-AD aMCI	-9.743	-20.083 – 0.597	.064
				CN vs. AD aMCI	-23.336	-34.465 – -12.206	<.001
				non-AD aMCI vs. AD aMCI	-13.593	-23.418 – -3.767	.007
	Section	0.140	.708				

	Diagnosis * Section	0.204	.816				
Allocentric heading task	Diagnosis	11.208	<.001	CN vs. non-AD aMCI	0.188	0.085 – 0.292	<.001
				CN vs. AD aMCI	0.257	0.146 – 0.368	<.001
				non-AD aMCI vs. AD aMCI	0.069	-0.030 – 0.167	.169
	Section	16.837	<.001	Section 1 vs. Section 2	0.191	0.100 – 0.282	<.001
	Diagnosis * Section	3.823	.023	Section 1: CN vs. non-AD aMCI	0.160	0.043 – 0.276	.007
				Section 1: CN vs. AD aMCI	0.178	0.055 – 0.302	.005
				Section 1: non-AD aMCI vs. AD aMCI	0.019	-0.096 – 0.133	.749
				Section 2: CN vs. non-AD aMCI	0.217	0.100 – 0.333	<.001
				Section 2: CN vs. AD aMCI	0.335	0.211 – 0.459	<.001
				Section 2: non-AD aMCI vs. AD aMCI	0.118	0.002 – 0.234	.045

F and *P* values refer to the main effect. $P_{post-hoc}$ values in bold were significant after FDR correction.

MMSE, Mini-Mental State Examination; 95% CI, 95% confidence interval; CN, cognitively normal; AD aMCI, amnesic mild cognitive impairment with positive Alzheimer's disease biomarkers; non-AD aMCI, amnesic mild cognitive impairment with negative Alzheimer's disease biomarkers.